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A STUDY OF PERSONALITY FACTORS AMONG LOW AND HIGH AGGRESSION OF SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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Abstract

Personality Trait, a psychological attribute influences the personal and social development of an individual. The present study was undertaken keeping these conditions in mind. Hence, the personality factor and adjustment their relations in male and female students were systematically measured and compared. Additionally the relationships of personality factor and adjustment with each other in both boys and girls separately and combining were also studied. For this, purpose 50 low and 50 high aggressive students of Bihar were availability selected and they were administered Personality Inventory (NEO – FFI) and aggression scale. The t- Test was applied to analyze the data. The results as follows: A significant difference between mean neuroticism scores of low and high aggressive students. While for, high aggressive students obtained significantly greater mean score on extraversion than low aggressive students meaning thereby that high aggressive students had significantly greater extraversion level than low aggressive students similarly, low aggressive students obtained significantly greater mean score on openness than high aggressive students. low aggressive students obtained significantly greater mean score on agreeableness than high aggressive students meaning thereby that low aggressive students had significantly agreeableness than low and high aggressive students and low aggressive students obtained significantly greater mean score on conscientiousness than low aggressive students meaning thereby that low aggressive students had significantly conscientiousness than high aggressive students were obtained. The study aims in making the school students aware of the various personality factor and the different aggression strategies that can help them deal with the problem in a better way, and thus maintaining their adjustment in family and school as well. The review concludes with a summary of major research findings, as well as a consideration of future directions and implications for practice and policy.

Keywords: *Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness, Aggression etc.*

Introduction

In the modern world, the child is the first priority, and longest lasting, context for development compared with other species, human children develop slowly, requiring years of support and teaching before they ready to be independent. Families are pervasive, and parents are universally important in children's lives. The attachments children form with parents and siblings usually last a lifetime, and they serve as models for relationship in the wider world of neighborhood and school. Within the family, children experience their first social conflict discipline by parents and arguments with siblings provide important lessons in compliance and cooperation and opportunities to learn how to influence the behavior of others. Finally, within the family, children learn the language, skills and social and moral values of their culture, and also the atmosphere, the experiences of childhood plays a very important role to built a personality and reduce aggressive behaviour.

In the life of a child, family, school, friends and other relatives are plays very important role and among the first function of the family, socialization has been greatest interest to child development socialization begins in earnest during the second year, once children are first able to comply with parental directives.

When the child is enter the period of adolescence, some traits are increase more. In which some certain psychological and emotional gap between parents and the adolescent girls or boys. The generation gap creates misunderstanding and lack of attachment between the parents and the children and the children loose their self-esteem and they are not achieve what they are expected. Only when we understand the reason of such kind of failure to achieve what they can, we can, help them to boost up their academic achievement, one such important factor which seems to emerge out from the various studies done so far is the typical personality organization of such a student.

Personality:

It is reasonably assumed that personality functions as a basis for all types of behavior. The person may or not be co-operative, may have more or less competitiveness, possesses positive or negative leadership qualities or may be emotionally stable or anxious. It all depends upon his personal make-up, Singer (1972) had also opined similarly, since personality determined by genetic factors but modified by environmental experience, a strong possibility exists that personality influences activity preferences as well as gets modified by activity experiences. The personality mould is formed early in life but can be changed by later experiences partly, if not completely.

As personality is reflective of the entire behavioral dimensions of individual, it has strong bearing on some variables also. Man's personality is the total picture of

behavior, which is made up of many components, some of which are objective and therefore, easily studied and measured. And some are subjective and cannot be measured easily. These objective components are physique, speed, strength and movement. The subjective components include motives, feeling, ideas, attitudes, character, will power etc. Personality according to Eysenck (1968). "It's a stable and enduring organization of person's character, temperaments, intellect and physique, which explains about the physiological differences between introverts and extroverts in the light of concept of weak and strong nervous system."

By examining the various approaches to the study and assessment of personality, the researcher came to the conclusion that the Big Five Model is one of the most comprehensive, empirical models. During the course of three or four decades of research, hundreds of personality measures and various phrases used to define personality were factor analysed in order to identify the essential, underlying components of personality. The findings showed five characteristics. The "Five Factor Model" is another name for these Big Five features (Costa and Mc Crae, 1992). Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism are the Big Five Factors (OCEAN). As a result, operational parameters investigated to evaluate personality were in line with NEO-FFI.

1. **Openness:** is a general appreciation for art, adventure, unusual ideas, and imagination. People who are open to experience are intellectually curious, appreciative of art, witty and sensitive to beauty. People with low scores on openness tend to have more conventional, traditional interests.
2. **Conscientiousness:** is a tendency to show self-discipline, act dutifully and aim for achievement. It includes the factor known as Need for Achievement. People high on this trait are generally achievement oriented, organised, responsible and dependable. On the negative side, they can be perfectionists or workaholic.
3. **Extraversion:** is characterized by positive emotions and the tendency to seek the company of others. Extroverts enjoy being with people and are energetic, dominant, assertive, outgoing, talking, fun-loving. Introverts, on the other hand, are quiet, less involved in external world and prefer to be alone.
4. **Agreeableness:** is a tendency to be compassionate and cooperative. Individuals high on this trait are considerate, friendly, generous, helpful, trustworthy, caring, warm and willing to

compromise their interests with others. They hold an optimistic view of human nature. People who score low are suspicious, unfriendly, and uncooperative and place self interest above getting along with others.

5. **Neuroticism:** is the tendency to experience negative emotions, such as anger, anxiety, fear etc. Those who score high on neuroticism are vulnerable to stress, more likely to interpret ordinary situations as threatening, emotionally unstable, anxious, worried, distressed, irritable and hypertensive. On the other hand, individuals who score low are emotionally stable, calm and free from persistent negative feelings.

This model represents a significant advancement in personality. In comprehending the profile across cultures, it has been shown to be helpful. The usefulness of the five dimensions in populations of the old and young, educated and illiterate, is further supported by cross-cultural researches. (Mc Crae and John, 1992).

Aggression:

‘The phenomenon in which one harms other to get joy’ - “The psychology of Aggression buss (1961)”. Aggression, in its broadest sense, is behavior, or a disposition, that is forceful, hostile or attacking. It may occur either in retaliation or without provocation. In narrower definitions that are used in social sciences and behavioral sciences, aggression is an intention to cause harm or an act intended to increase relative social dominance. Predatory or defensive behavior between members of different species may not be considered aggression in the same sense. Aggression can take a variety of forms and can be physical or be communicated verbally or non-verbally. Aggression differs from what is commonly called assertiveness, although the terms are often used interchangeably among laypeople, e.g. an aggressive salesperson.

Two broad categories of aggression are commonly distinguished. One includes affective (emotional) and hostile or retaliatory aggression, and the other includes instrumental, goal-oriented or predatory aggression. Data on violence from a range of disciplines lend some support to a distinction between affective and predatory aggression. However, some researchers question the usefulness of a hostile vs instrumental distinction in humans, despite its ubiquity in research, because most real-life cases involve mixed motives and interacting causes. A number of classifications and dimensions of aggression have been suggested. These depend on such things as whether the aggression is

verbal or physical; whether or not it involves relational aggression such as covert bullying and social manipulation; whether harm to others is intended or not; whether it is carried out actively or expressed passively; and whether the aggression is aimed directly or indirectly. Classification may also encompass aggression-related emotions (e.g. anger) and mental states (e.g. impulsivity, hostility). Aggression may occur in response to non-social as well as social factors, and can have a close relationship with stress coping style. Aggression may be displayed in order to intimidate.

The operative definition of aggression may be affected by moral or political views. Examples are the axiomatic moral view called the nonaggression principle and the political rules governing the behavior of one country toward another. Likewise in competitive sports, or in the workplace, some forms of aggression may be sanctioned and others not.

Significant of the study:

The most distinctive feature of any individual is his personality. This is the overall pattern, or integration of his structure, modes of behavior, interests, attitudes, intellectual abilities, and aptitudes and, many other distinguishable characteristics. Thus the term personality refers to the whole individual. Viewing a person as he goes about the various activities of his everyday life, we usually obtain a total impression of his personality as “agreeable”, “disagreeable”, “dominating”, “submissive”, or the like. Psychology, however, views the individual more analytically. Little can be done scientifically with an overall impression. The reduce aggressive behavior helps man to make better beings. Most of the individual try to stabilize themselves in different aspects of their personality. Opportunities are varied and it is at the high school level. That most personality are exposed to being adjusted person at some point of time. They are further challenged from different angles to develop this personality as they are involved in all the activities of the school and colleges. This study is significant as it provides an insight into the personality and aggressive behavior of students in Bihar district. Every student must adjust to his environment according to the situations. The degree of personality and aggression varies from person to person. Adolescence is a highly critical period in the life of all. The complexity further increases and the students gets frustrated when he is not able to cope up with the sudden changes that takes place during this period at home, school and peer group.

Hypothesis: There would be a significant difference between high and low aggression on different factors of personality.

Sample:

Purposive sampling was used in this research. Purposive sampling is a method adopted by researchers where data is collected from particular units of the universe for constituting a sample that represents the universe. It is most commonly used for sampling hours, as it is uncomplicated and economical in many cases. A total of 100 samples of senior secondary school students were randomly selected from Bihar School. The sample consisted of 50 students were having low level of aggression and 50 students were having high level of aggression.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

In the present study a two groups design (high and low aggression) was used. Present study was to examine the difference between high and low aggression on different factors of personality. So, Therefore, two group design was used in this research.

TOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION:

There were two tools used for data collection.

1. **Personality Inventory (NEO – FFI) by Paul T. Costa and Robert Mc Crae (1992)** was used to assess personality factors. The NEO – FFI is a short form of the Revised NEO Personality Inventory. This personality inventory assesses five dimensions of personality namely Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. This inventory is based on the five factor model of personality. The Inventory consists of 60 items with 12 items assessing each personality factor. The items are rated on a five point scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Responses are added on each dimension to get the total score on each personality factor. Costa and Mc Crae (1992) report that the NEO FFI scales are highly reliable and strongly correlated with the corresponding domain scales of the full NEO PI – R (convergent reliability ranged from 0.77 to 0.94 across various samples).
2. **Aggression Questionnaire (AQ; Buss & Perry, 1992):** The Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BAQ) is one of the most widely used aggression scales. BAQ is a

self-report scale consisting of 29 items answered on a 5-point Likert-type scale that was adapted from the Buss-Durkee Hostility Inventory (BDHI) (Buss and Durkee 1957). Its 4 subscales measure physical aggression, verbal aggression, hostility, and anger. The physical aggression subscale includes 9 items about physically harming others, the verbal aggression subscale includes 5 items about verbal aggression directed towards others, the anger subscale includes 7 items that measure the affective aspect of aggression, and the hostility subscale includes 8 items that assess the cognitive aspect of aggression. Scores for each item were added to obtain the dimension score, and dimension scores were summed to obtain the total score. Cronbach Coefficient was reported 0.83.

Results and Discussion:

Hypothesis-1: There would be a significant difference between high and low aggression on different factors of personality.

	Gro ups	N	Me an	SD	S E D	t	Si g. L e v el
Neuroti cism	Lo w agg ress ive	50	24.64	6.94	1.639	10.870	<.01
	Hig hly agg ress ive	50	42.46	9.64			
Extrave rsion	Lo w agg ress ive	50	29.34	9.23	1.765	12.023	<.01
	Hig hly agg ress ive	50	50.56	8.385			

Openness	Low aggressive	50	46.74	10.059	1.719	8.320	<.01
	Highly aggressive	50	32.44	6.822			
Agreeableness	Low aggressive	50	35.29	10.059	1.843	10.560	<.01
	Highly aggressive	50	54.74	7.855			
Conscientiousness	Low aggressive	50	22.19	12.219	2.140	2.477	<.01
	Highly aggressive	50	50.48	8.924			

Table no.: Means, SDs, and SED and results of t-ratio of high and low aggressive students on Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness

Figure: Graphic representation of mean score of Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness of two high and low aggressive students.

Table- 5.2 shows that score Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness scores of low aggressive students were 24.64, 29.34, 46.74, 35.28, and 55.78 respectively and mean scores of highly aggressive students were 42.46, 50.56, 32.44, 54.74 and 50.48 respectively and their respective SDs of male were 6.694, 9.243, 10.059, 10.396 and 12.219 respectively and SDs of female were 9.464, 8.385, 6.822, 7.855 and 8.924 respectively. Their respective SED were 1.639, 1.765, 1.719, 1.843 and 2.140. The t- ratios between means Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness scores of the two groups were found as 1.639, 12.023, 8.320, 10.560 and 2.477 which was significant at level of 0.01. It means that there is statistical difference on the scores of Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness between high and low aggressive students. The findings of the present study did confirm the hypothesis -1 which states that “there would be a significant difference between high and low aggression on different factors of personality” was proved true by the finding of the study.

Our results imply that those high in Neuroticism and low in Agreeableness and Conscientiousness are at higher risk of exhibiting aggressive behavior. Neuroticism describes the overall tendency to experience negative emotions (Costa & McCrae, 2005), including higher stress reactivity, increased feelings of hostility and anger, poor impulse control, and increased sensitivity to frustration and provocations (Bettencourt et al., 2006; Zajenkovska et al., 2013). The use of the narrower sub facets allowed for a parsing of the trait level findings. While all six Neuroticism sub facets demonstrated significant associations with trait aggression, the facets of Angry Hostility and Impulsivity presented with the strongest relationship, indicating that the propensity to feel angry hostile emotions and poor impulse control are more fundamental to aggressive behaviors than other Neuroticism subfacets (e.g., Anxiety and Self-consciousness). However, this observation may be partly explained by significant predictor-criterion overlap in the questionnaires used, particularly for the two BPAQ subscales designed to assess traits related to anger and hostility. Although FFM is a result of basic personality research and do not explicitly reference aggressive acts, some items on the NEO and BPAQ questionnaire are close to identical: For example, “I am perceived as fiery and temperamental” from Neuroticism subfacet Angry Hostility and “Some of my friends think I am a hothead” from BPAQ subscale Anger. Thus, it is not surprising that the

Angry Hostility subfacet of the NEO PI-R is such a strong correlate to BPAQ.

The central role of Agreeableness in aggression is well documented (Jones et al., 2011; Miller & Lynam, 2001) and our findings align with previous results. While the narrower subfacets analyses showed that four of six Agreeableness facets demonstrated significant negative relation to trait aggression, the facets of Trust, Altruism and Compliance, presented with the strongest negative relationship. According to Costa and McCrae (2005), high levels of Agreeableness promote prosocial behaviors such as cooperativeness, kindness, and altruism, while low Agreeableness promote the tendency to feel less sympathy and empathy toward others (Graziano et al., 2007). Thus, low Agreeableness may lead to an increase in interpersonal conflict through the disinhibition of social and relational regulatory mechanisms mediated by lack of empathic attunement which allows the individual to more easily act on their aggressive and violent impulses (Bettencourt et al., 2006). Interestingly, evidence suggest that the presence of high Neuroticism may not be sufficient to promote aggressive and violent behavior on its own but instead must be in conjunction with low Agreeableness (Ode et al., 2008). Thus, one way to interpret the interaction between Neuroticism and Agreeableness is that the negative bias and emotional dysregulation indexed by high Neuroticism makes the individual more sensitive to situational triggers such as provocations or perceived insults which in combination with low Agreeableness, may facilitate hostile and aggressive behavior. This could in turn contribute to the negative effect on mental health associated with high Neuroticism, as repeated antagonistic and confrontational interactions with others might enforce the tendency to interpret the world and the motivations of others negatively (Costa & McCrae, 2005).

Conscientiousness describes the propensity to be deliberate, goal-oriented, and disciplined (Costa & McCrae, 2005). Within the literature, a small but consistent negative association has been reported (Jones et al., 2011), matching our findings in the present study. The narrower subfacets analyses showed that four of six Conscientiousness facets demonstrated small but statistically significant negative relation to trait aggression: Deliberation, Self-discipline, Dutifulness, and Competence. The link between Conscientiousness and aggression is less clear than those of Neuroticism and Agreeableness, but one interpretation may be that individuals low on Conscientiousness are more impulsive and focus less on the potential consequences of their actions and thus are less deterred by the negative social consequences of aggressive and disruptive behaviors.

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